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RESEARCH ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL "CHINESE-STYLE APPROACH" TO NATIONAL CONDITIONS EDUCATION FOR INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS

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Globalization continues to drive the internationalization of higher education. However, anti-globalization, ideological frictions, biased Western media, and cross-cultural psychological conflicts have led to misunderstandings of China among international students. Based on top-level design, systematic curriculum construction, and psychological adaptation support, China has explored a diversified and systematic "Chinese-style Approach" to national conditions education for international students. This approach helps international students understand China comprehensively, enhances their cross-cultural identity and mental adaptation, cultivates international talents who know and are friendly to China, and spreads an authentic national image. It also provides valuable experience for Russia and other countries to improve the training quality of international students.

Keywords: International student education; National conditions education; Chinese-style Approach; Psychological perspective; Cross-cultural adaptation

INTRODUCTION

Global integration and globalization in politics, economics, and culture expand international contacts and result in higher education internationalization through the export of educational programs and academic mobility[1]. However, the rising tide of anti-globalization in the world makes it more and more difficult to train international students. Meanwhile, the rapid development of social media has also amplified this contradiction, resulting in the deviation or even misunderstanding of international students' cognition of the country where they study. Although the general trend of globalization of education will not change, the influence of the anti-globalization trend of thought has increased the difficulty of training education for international students. China and Russia are both educational powers with a large number of international students. China has become the largest destination country for overseas study in Asia. Data show that the number of overseas students coming to China from 2013 to 2020 shows an increasing trend year by year, rising from 328,000 in 2013 to 492,000 in 2019 [2]. In addition, the Western media have long reported on China in an unobjective and one-sided way, which has led to the misunderstanding of foreign people about China's national conditions and its image. The experience and lessons of China's national conditions education in recent years can provide a reference for Russia, and the "Chinese-style

Approach" of international students' ideological education discussed in this paper can also provide certain ideas and innovations for Russia to train international students better. For a long time, China has attached great importance to the training of talents studying in China and put the education of China's national conditions in an important position. In March 2017, the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and the Ministry of Public Security jointly formulated the Administrative Measures for the Recruitment and Training of International Students in Schools, which stipulated that Chinese language courses and courses about China should be compulsory courses for international students with higher degrees. The following year, the Ministry of Education of China issued the Standard for the Quality of Higher Education for International Students in China (Trial), emphasizing that international students should be familiar with China's national conditions and basic cultural knowledge. In May 2020, Chinese leaders sent a letter to international students in Pakistan expressing their expectations for international youth's further education and exchanges, which guided the current national conditions of education activities for international students [3]. For most international students, due to differences in culture, history, religion, social background, and experience, their understanding of China is also different. Coupled with false reports by some foreign media, many international students' understanding of today's China is scattered, superficial, one-sided, and some even wrong.

PRESENTATION OF THE MAIN MATERIAL

Dilemmas of national conditions education. The first is the dilemma of cross-cultural communication. Chinese culture is different from other cultures in the world, but it is also easy to produce communication barriers, and the rampant "clash of civilizations" weakens the basis of identity, which is a significant representation of the present. Language barriers, contextual differences between mother culture and other cultures, and cultural tolerance are all important factors affecting cross-cultural communication. According to the theory of psychological culturology, at the level of international communication, culture not only plays an important role in determining the goals of a country's foreign policy but also has an important impact on the process of foreign policy formulation, the mode, and style of diplomacy of a country [4]. However, such "view" and "mode" will change with the interactive situation of cultural exchanges [5]. The second is the dilemma of international public opinion. In the international discourse system, China has long been faced with the dilemma of "not being able to say what is right, not being able to spread what is said, and no one believing it", presenting a weak position in international public opinion. In the past, China's national image was mostly shaped based on the needs of other countries themselves. From the "sick man of East Asia" at that time to the "China threat" today, the "discourse signal" that equates the community of human destiny with the "hegemony of Chinese civilization" is not only an image label imposed by the outside world [6]. Such other-image-making "is never a self-contained, objectified product, but is made according to the ego's imagination of the 'other', that is, a creative fabrication of the other according to the needs of the ego, a projection of the image-makers desires" [7]. To change the "other molded" China in the eyes of the world, China itself speaks China, and international students in China are undoubtedly an important channel. Finally, the internal

dilemma of the national education system. On the one hand, some Chinese universities blindly recruit international students and set up international exchange programs. Compared with the starting point of the cultivation plan, the curriculum teaching and professional practice of international students' national education has problems such as not being implemented in place, being superficial and not deeply cultivating the teaching purpose, and also deviates from the original intention of improving the level of international education. In addition, some colleges and universities in China lack a national education and teaching system, there are many problems such as irregular construction of teaching materials, uneven teaching progress, in-depth teaching and research content, and even not being included in the overall planning of the school. There is a "scattered and poor" phenomenon in practical education activities, which lacks strong social force support and educational resources support.

Role of higher education. The internationalization of higher education has played a significant role in regional transformations and has brought about important global shifts [8]. With the rapid development of China, "Chinese governance", "Chinese system" and "China's achievements" have attracted more and more attention. Making full use of the education platform of colleges and universities in China, promoting the education of China's national conditions, training international students to become international talents who know and are friends with China, and turning international students interested in China into "China experts" through national conditions education is also one of the purposes of receiving international students in China. The government authorities and the international student education system in colleges and universities should establish a joint mechanism. National education for international students should be incorporated into the work of the government and the work plan for the training of international students in colleges and universities, so as to coordinate the promotion of national education in colleges and universities and promote the process of substantive construction. The Ministry of Education of China should guide Chinese colleges and universities to correctly understand the connotation of "diversified education", clarify the educational goals and means of international students, comprehensively and systematically build a national education system, clarify the guiding ideology of national education, curriculum construction principles, curriculum education goals and Outlines, as well as the selection standards of textbooks and the teaching methods combining online and offline. Secondly, China should establish and perfect the national education system of university linkage and strengthen the inter-school curriculum alliance. The national conditions education should be included in the work planning of international student education in universities, the real implementation of national conditions education in the system, and the top-level design at the university level should be strengthened. The Ministry of Education of China will set up a national conditions education curriculum construction group to give full play to the high-quality resources of national conditions education on campus, systematically, scientifically, and pertinently plan and develop the curriculum system, and combine the curriculum connotation with the professional distribution and group characteristics of international students in schools in a targeted manner, to effectively crack the bias and misunderstanding of China's image deliberately created by international public opinion.

Third, colleges and universities should establish a sound international student work system and strive to improve the internationalization level of teachers. Chinese colleges and universities need to fully integrate international student work into the school student work system, advocate the study of Tsinghua University's international student work guidance concept of "convergence and differentiation management, integrated development, and comprehensive improvement", and form the International Office, Student department, graduate work Department as the business guidance department, and rely on the student work team of each department. The work system and collaborative work mechanism covering all international students shall be established to improve the international student guidance system [9]. Colleges and universities can incorporate international students into the regularized student management and assistance system, give full play to the professional service capacity of departments of psychological counseling, career guidance, learning, global competence cultivation, etc., and provide targeted guidance and support for international students. At the same time, the internationalization level of the faculty is cultivated and developed in it. The author suggests that the Chinese education authorities and other specialized agencies set up supervisory groups to regularly supervise the implementation of national education in colleges and universities, to promote field research and differential assessment of national education in colleges and universities; and to conduct questionnaire surveys on international students to assess the actual effects of education in colleges and universities. Based on the results of the monitoring, evaluation, and assessment of colleges and universities, the Chinese education authorities constantly put forward new requirements and standards for the national education of international students in colleges and universities. According to the actual situation of national education, colleges, and universities explore and formulate the actual evaluation standard of the quality of national education, taking the effectiveness of national image building as an important index, while strengthening the evaluation of students' learning effect and timely understanding of students' opinions and suggestions on national education [10].

Curriculum optimization. Firstly, it is necessary to comprehensively promote the effective connection between the construction of national education courses and the needs of international students. In October 2018, China's Ministry of Education issued the Quality Standards for the Education of International Students in Higher Education Institutions (for Trial Implementation), which requires higher education institutions to supplement and improve the elements and links of their internal education quality assurance system according to the characteristics of the education of international students and meet the needs of the quality assurance of the education of international students in China; and, while enriching the connotation of national education, it is more important to be close to the needs and thoughts of international students and fully consider their interests and emotions. Colleges and universities should understand what international students are most concerned about, and answer practical and background questions related to China's history and system, foreign policy, economic environment, employment environment, and so on, to meet the needs of international students for the vision of China's national conditions education. Secondly, it is necessary to promote the systematic construction of Chinese language international education courses and facilitate the

transformation of Chinese language education into specialization and practicality. In terms of content and framework, Chinese universities should cover the basic theory of the subject, the theory of the application of the subject, the theory of regional, national, and language characteristics of Chinese education, and the theory of interdisciplinary integration [11]. The third is to create high-quality national education courses, leading the construction of a high-quality cross-cultural curriculum system. In June 2017, China's Ministry of Education and others announced the "Management Measures for the Recruitment and Training of International Students in Schools", which included the Chinese language and the general situation of China in the management of the national compulsory higher education curriculum system. It is worth mentioning that the "China Overview" series of teaching videos jointly created by experts and scholars from more than 10 famous universities such as Peking University, Beijing Normal University, and Nanjing University were released on the MOOC (MOOC) platform of Chinese universities. Finally, we should promote the internationalization of regional cultural narration and dissemination to contribute to national conditions education. Regional culture, as the characteristic culture of international students' residence, is also the most specific Chinese culture that international students have contact with. The course Shanghai City Culture, which has been offered by the School of International Chinese Culture of East China Normal University for more than ten years, sets a model for the transformation of regional cultural narration and dissemination. The course focuses on teaching the history, economy, folk culture, and other contents in the process of Shanghai's urban development to international students, and deeply explores the value and significance of regional culture to national conditions education [12].

Second classroom practice. The second classroom enriches practical forms to consolidate classroom knowledge. The concept of the second classroom is introduced in Chinese universities, which refers to the teaching activities related to the first classroom in the time outside the first classroom, to promote the national education curriculum to be more three-dimensional. To enhance the cultural experience of international students, organize visits to local museums, science and technology museums, and art galleries, and feel the unique cultural atmosphere; In addition, colleges and universities can make full use of their websites and WeChat public accounts to organize cultural knowledge Q&A activities, so that international students can actively participate in them. While enriching the daily life of international students, they can promote their learning of excellent traditional Chinese culture, deepen their cognition of Chinese culture, strengthen their understanding, love, and dissemination of Chinese traditional culture, and let more people know about China and love Chinese culture [13]. Guide international students to experience the development of China with the content they have seen, heard, and experienced with their own eyes. At the same time, they can also expand the national conditions education space with the help of financial media, and promote the international dissemination of vivid images of China. As the digital and networked space continues to expand, Chinese mainstream media such as People's Daily, Xinhua News Agency, CCTV, and China Daily have produced a large number of integrated media products geared towards international dissemination. For example, several new media programs such as "Interpreting China" and "China Road" have become internationally renowned intellectual

property IPs [14]. In addition, practical courses are crucial for international students, and they help them better integrate into the local cultural and social environment. By interacting with local classmates and teachers, international students can promote cross-cultural communication and understanding. In the process, international students have the opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of Chinese customs, values, and social norms, thus integrating more deeply into their new environment.

CONCLUSION

In terms of cross-cultural education itself, knowledge teaching integrated into specific historical and cultural environments can make it easier for international students to understand. At present, the understanding of Chinese history and culture of some international students in China is limited to modern China. Due to different cultural backgrounds, knowledge systems, and the diversity of Chinese history and culture, it is difficult for international students in China to connect today's Chinese society and culture with the characteristics of Chinese civilization stretching for thousands of years, and it is difficult for them to understand China from the perspective of Chinese spirit and civilization characteristics. In intercultural teaching, a better understanding of China can help international students adapt to Chinese teaching models and methods, and establish friendships with Chinese teachers and students to achieve better learning of professional knowledge. Especially in the field of humanities and social sciences, only by allowing international students to have a deep understanding of China's national conditions history, and culture can they do well in the research of topics related to China's diplomatic, economic, social, and political development. Both China and Russia are world powers with a long history and culture and a vast territory. Politically, both countries are subjected to sanctions and pressure from many aspects of Western countries. Economically, both countries are in a critical period of economic transformation and rapid rise; In terms of external communication, both countries are in a relatively weak position in terms of the right to speak international public opinion, and need to further improve their international communication capabilities [15]. Therefore, Russia can learn from the model or strategy of China's national conditions of education in universities. Russian universities will introduce the national conditions of Russia or carry out relevant cultural practice activities for international students when teaching international students in Russia. However, it is entirely possible to elevate this beneficial practice into a course and constantly enhance its status and influence in the education of international students. In this way, the profound history and culture of the two countries can be better used to attract international students. Universities in Western countries, especially those in English-speaking countries, have an absolute advantage in language. To compete with them, China and Russia should develop more attractive national characteristics, especially cultural characteristics [16]. This also coincides with the idea of carrying out national conditions education in Chinese universities. International students are young groups with broad vision and active thinking, and their cross-cultural adaptability is relatively strong. However, like other groups, international students inevitably feel cross-cultural pressure after entering the host

country, which comes from the strong impact of the formation of different cultures and the cultural identity troubles experienced by international students [17].

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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО «КИТАЙСКОГО
ПОДХОДА» К ОБУЧЕНИЮ ИНОСТРАННЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ С УЧЁТОМ
НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ

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Глобализация продолжает стимулировать интернационализацию высшего образования. Однако антиглобалистские настроения, идеологические противоречия, предвзятые западные СМИ и межкультурные психологические конфликты привели к искажённому восприятию Китая среди иностранных студентов. Опираясь на высокий уровень проектирования, систематическое построение учебных программ и поддержку психологической адаптации, Китай разработал диверсифицированный и системный «китайский подход» к обучению иностранных студентов в национальных условиях. Такой подход помогает иностранным студентам всесторонне понять Китай, повышает их межкультурную идентичность и ментальную адаптацию, воспитывает международных специалистов, которые знают Китай и относятся к нему дружелюбно, а также способствует распространению подлинного национального имиджа. Данный опыт имеет важное значение для России и других стран, стремящихся повысить качество обучения иностранных студентов.

Ключевые слова: Международное студенческое образование; Образование в национальных условиях; Подход в китайском стиле; Психологический аспект; Кросс-культурная адаптация

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